

QUARTERLY TEAM SURVEY TEMPLATE

PROCESS				
1	Agile		I am happy with Agile Practices and ceremonies	Doing Good
			We have to improve on Agile Practices & ceremonies	Doing Okay
			I am unhappy with Agile Practices and ceremonies	Disaster
2	Accepting New Requirements		We are able to accept and complete last-minute request/changes	Doing Good
			We are facing challenges in accommodating last minute request/changes	Doing Okay
			We resist/don't accept last minute request/changes	Disaster
3	Empowerment		We are empowered to estimate, pick and implement the stories.	Doing Good
			Sometimes, we are overridden by the leads.	Doing Okay
			We are forced to execute the way our leads want	Disaster
PRODUCT				
4	Delivering Value		We are working on business-critical stories.	Doing Good
			We don't have clarity if my story delivers value.	Doing Okay
			We are spending time on trivial stories that delivers less customer value.	Disaster
5	Roadmap		We know the product roadmap.	Doing Good
			We don't have clarity on Roadmap	Doing Okay
			We don't have Roadmap	Disaster
6	Product Quality		We are delivering high quality software (No severity bugs identified during/after the release)	Doing Good
			We are delivering good quality software but there are bugs during/after the release.	Doing Okay
			We deliver poor quality software (Production bugs/Incidents raised after/during the release)	Disaster
7	Release Validation		Our release validation process is very tight and my confidence level is very high	Doing Good
			Our release validation is good, but it is still not fool proof	Doing Okay
			There are ALWAYS defects leaking even after release validation process	Disaster
INNOVATION				

8	Learning		We get enough opportunity to learn in this team.	Doing Good
			We get limited opportunity to learn in this team.	Doing Okay
			We don't get opportunity to learn as part of this team.	Disaster
9	Idea generation		Team listens to my ideas/thought process and supports me in taking it forward	Doing Good
			Team listens to my ideas/thought process but it is not taken forward.	Doing Okay
			I rarely get a platform to share my ideas	Disaster
PEOPLE				
10	Help		People jump to help me out of crisis	Doing Good
			I need followup and multiple requests for help	Doing Okay
			My cry for help in the team is never heard	Disaster
11	Team		We are functioning as ONE team.	Doing Good
			There are instances when team members work in isolation	Doing Okay
			We are a dysfunctional team.	Disaster
12	Appreciation		I get appreciated whenever I do a great job	Doing Good
			I rarely get appreciated, despite my smart work.	Doing Okay
			I don't get appreciated at all.	Disaster
13	Fun		I am having fun at my work place	Doing Good
			I am not having enough fun at my work place	Doing Okay
			I do not have any fun at work place	Disaster
LEADERSHIP				
14	Support		Leadership Team voluntarily reaches out to the team and supports them.	Doing Good
			Leadership Team is available but the suggestions are in conflicting directions	Doing Okay
			Leadership Team is unavailable when needed.	Disaster
15	Support		Leadership Team demonstrates focused attention across all areas	Doing Good
			Leadership Team focuses on a limited number of areas	Doing Okay
			Leadership Team lacks focus	Disaster